

A Rationale to Foster the Role of Energy Communities in Creating Inclusive Social Hubs for Citizen Science in Energy Aspects.

Matevž Bokalič^{1*} (0000-0003-1071-9134), A.B.Cristóbal² (0000-0002-4314-6160), Marta Victoria³ (0000-0003-1665-1281), Afonso Cavaco⁴ (0000-0001-8112-1696), Emma Williams⁵, Alexander Gerber⁶ (0000-0002-9737-1267), Martin Brocklehurst⁷, Marko Topič¹ (0000-0001-8089-2974).

1*: Univerza v Ljubljani,
Fakulteta za elektrotehniko,
Tržaška cesta 25, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia
Email: matevz.bokalic@fe.uni-lj.si

2: Instituto de Energía Solar,
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
Instituto de Energía Solar
C/Alan Turing s/n, 28031, Madrid, Spain

3: Aarhus University,
Department of Mechanical and Production
Engineering,
Katrinebjergvej 89 G-F, 8200 Aarhus N,
Denmark

4: Universidade de Évora, Renewable Energies
Chair,
Largo dos Colegiais, N° 2, 7004-516 Évora,
Portugal

5: Forest of Dean District Council
Council Offices High Street
Coleford GL16 8HG, United Kingdom

6: Institute for Science & Innovation
Communication (insico)
Briener Str. 25, 47533 Kleve, Germany

7: Kempley Green Consultants
Kempley GL128 2BW, United Kingdom

Keywords: Energy Communities, behaviour, citizen science, energy transition, universities

Abstract

Addressing the detrimental impact of our energy habits on the climate presents a complex challenge, with no simple solution. Nevertheless, fostering behavioural changes towards sustainability remains a crucial component of the solution. Promoting individual and collective awareness plays a crucial role, and citizen science hubs can significantly contribute to this endeavour.

This paper introduces the Aurora project, which seeks to create citizen science hubs as community-driven centres for promoting renewable energy adoption. By establishing community crowdfunded photovoltaic plants across five diverse locations in Europe, including four university environments and one rural area, the project aims to transform existing communities into renewable energy communities. To support this endeavour, the Aurora App is introduced, offering users a means to track their energy-related carbon footprint, receive personalized impact information, and provide suggestions for minimizing their carbon footprint. Moreover, users can offset their emissions by participating in the photovoltaic installations. The project also incorporates promotional and educational activities designed to raise awareness, engage community members, and drive behavioural changes.

We focus on the efforts to establish appropriate legal entities and communities for the photovoltaic demonstrators. Furthermore, we highlight the role of public universities as catalysts in promoting and supporting such citizen science hubs. We conclude with an invitation for ambassadors to propagate the Aurora project's concept within their own social communities, further expanding project's positive impact.